

ISic0133

I.Sicily inscription 0133

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arco) · Arrunti[o][---]

2. Brocc[ho][---]

3. [l]ocus · pu[b]lic(e) · d[atus]

4. ex · d(ecreto) · d(ecurionum) · in · fr[ontep(edes)---]

5. in · agro · p(edes) · XX[---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To Marcus Arruntius Brocc[hus]. (This) burial plot was granted, at public expense, by the decree of the town council. In width [...] feet, in depth [at least 20?] feet...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285239

EDR 111014
EDCS 22100078

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7377 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650798>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 52

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